

PERISCOPING POLITICAL PATRONAGE AND DEVELOPMENT OF DEMOCRACY IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Keywords:

Political patronage, democracy, patronage-based political appointments, political participation, democratic institutions.

Abstract: *The study examined the relationship between political patronage and development of democracy in Anambra State. The specific objectives of the study are; to examine the effect of patronage-based political appointments on political accountability in Anambra State, ascertain the effect of the distribution of government contracts to political allies on citizens' political participation in Anambra State, and to explore the effect of patronage-driven allocation of public resources on public trust in democratic institutions in Anambra State. In line with these objectives, three research questions and corresponding hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study was hinged on the Elite Theory which was first systematically articulated by Gaetano Mosca (1939) and later developed by Vilfredo Pareto (1968) and C. Wright Mills (1956). A descriptive survey research design was adopted, with a population of three hundred and twenty-eight (328) selected residents of Anambra State who were considered knowledgeable about political activities and governance in the state. Data were collected from both primary and secondary sources, with a structured questionnaire serving as the primary instrument for data collection. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and mean scores, while the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) techniques, through the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 26 was used to test the hypotheses. The findings revealed that; patronage-based political appointments have significant negative effect on political accountability in Anambra State; the distribution of government contracts to political allies has significant negative effect on citizens' political participation in Anambra State, and that patronage-driven allocation of public resources has significant negative effect on public trust in democratic institutions in*

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Anambra State. Based on the findings, the study concluded that political patronage negatively impacts the development of democracy in Anambra State. It recommends among other things that government and political stakeholders should adopt transparent and merit-based appointment processes for public offices to strengthen political accountability. Ensuring that qualified individuals occupy key positions will enhance oversight, reduce corruption, and promote good governance.

1. Introduction

The consolidation of democracy across many parts of the world has remained closely linked with the nature of political relationships that exist between political actors and citizens. Among the most debated of such relationships is political patronage, a phenomenon that has continued to shape political behaviour, governance outcomes, and democratic development, particularly in developing democracies. Political patronage generally refers to the distribution of public offices, resources, contracts, or other benefits by political leaders to supporters, loyalists, or political allies in exchange for political support and loyalty (Aiyede, 2018). While patronage networks have historically been present in many political systems, their persistence and influence in emerging democracies have raised concerns about their implications for democratic accountability, transparency, and institutional development. Scholars have argued that patronage politics often weakens democratic institutions by prioritizing loyalty over

competence and by encouraging the personalization of political power (Bratton & Van de Walle, 2018). In this regard, the interaction between political patronage and democratic development has become a subject of significant scholarly interest, particularly in African countries where democratic institutions are still evolving.

In the African context, the entrenchment of patronage politics has been widely documented as a defining feature of political competition and governance. Many African political systems are characterized by clientelistic networks in which political leaders distribute state resources to maintain political support and consolidate their influence. According to Erdmann and Engel (2019), patron–client relationships remain central to the functioning of many African democracies because political elites often rely on such networks to mobilize electoral support and maintain political stability. Although patronage may sometimes serve as a mechanism for political inclusion or conflict management, its dominance in political systems can undermine

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democratic principles such as meritocracy, fairness, and accountability. Consequently, the prevalence of patronage politics has raised questions about the depth and quality of democratic governance across the continent. Studies have also shown that patronage politics often results in the misallocation of public resources and the marginalization of citizens who are not connected to political elites (Kramon & Posner, 2016).

In Nigeria, political patronage has become a prominent feature of the country's democratic experience since the return to civilian rule in 1999. Nigeria operates a multi-party democratic system that is expected to promote popular participation, political competition, and accountability. However, the practice of patronage politics has continued to influence the political landscape, often shaping electoral processes, political appointments, and policy implementation. Several scholars have argued that political patronage in Nigeria manifests through the appointment of loyal party members into public offices, the awarding of government contracts to political allies, and the distribution of material incentives to voters during elections (Aiyede, 2018; Omotola, 2019). These practices have significant implications for democratic development because they can undermine institutional integrity and encourage political corruption. Similarly, Okeke and Eme (2020)

observed that patronage politics often weakens democratic accountability by creating a system where political loyalty is rewarded above competence and public interest. In this regard, Chukwuemeka, Chinenye, and Okafor (2018), argued that the effectiveness of public institutions and service delivery in Nigeria can be strengthened through governance reforms such as e-governance initiatives, highlighting the critical link between institutional integrity, administrative efficiency, and citizens' trust in democratic processes.

The influence of political patronage is particularly evident in the political dynamics of many Nigerian states, including Anambra State. Since the restoration of democratic governance in Nigeria, Anambra State has witnessed intense political competition and the emergence of powerful political actors who often play significant roles in determining electoral outcomes. The state's political history has been characterized by episodes of political godfatherism, party defections, and patronage-based political alliances that have shaped governance and democratic practices. Scholars have noted that political patronage in the state often manifests through political appointments, the distribution of state resources, and the mobilization of supporters during electoral contests (Onyekwelu & Okafor, 2022). While such practices may sometimes strengthen

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political networks and enhance political mobilization, they also raise concerns about their impact on democratic consolidation and good governance.

Given the continued relevance of patronage politics in Nigerian political life and its potential implications for democratic governance, it becomes important to examine how political patronage influences the development of democracy at the subnational level. It is against this backdrop that this study examines the relationship between political patronage and development of democracy in Anambra State.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Democratic governance ideally thrives on principles such as accountability, transparency, political participation, and the equitable distribution of public resources. In a well-functioning democratic system, political leaders are expected to prioritize public interest, promote merit-based appointments, and ensure that governance structures operate in ways that strengthen institutions and uphold the rule of law. The development of democracy is also expected to encourage inclusive governance where citizens have equal opportunities to participate in political processes without undue influence from elite networks or personal loyalties. In such a system, public offices and state resources are managed in a manner that supports socio-economic development,

strengthens public trust in government, and promotes fairness in political competition. Democratic institutions are therefore expected to operate independently of personal or political interests, thereby ensuring that governance outcomes reflect the collective will and aspirations of the people. When democratic principles function effectively, political leaders are held accountable for their actions, electoral processes remain credible, and governance structures are strengthened to deliver sustainable development and political stability within society.

However, in many developing democracies, including Nigeria, political processes are often influenced by complex networks of political relationships that may shape how public resources and opportunities are distributed. In some cases, the practice of political patronage has been discussed in relation to the allocation of political appointments, the distribution of government contracts, and the mobilization of political support during elections. Within the context of Anambra State, political dynamics over the years have generated debates among scholars, observers, and citizens regarding the extent to which patronage networks may influence democratic governance and political decision-making. While some observers suggest that political patronage may serve as a mechanism for political mobilization and

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alliance-building, others question whether such practices could affect institutional development, accountability, or the broader democratic process. Despite these discussions, it remains uncertain how political patronage actually interacts with democratic development within the specific political environment of Anambra State, thereby creating the need for a deeper empirical investigation into the phenomenon.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to examine the relationship between political patronage and development of democracy in Anambra State. The specific objectives of the study are;

- i. To examine the effect of patronage-based political appointments on political accountability in Anambra State.
- ii. To ascertain the effect of the distribution of government contracts to political allies on citizens' political participation in Anambra State.
- iii. To explore the effect of patronage-driven allocation of public resources on public trust in democratic institutions in Anambra State.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions will guide the study:

- i. To what extent does patronage-based political appointments affect political accountability in Anambra State?

- ii. How does the distribution of government contracts to political allies affect citizens' political participation in Anambra State?
- iii. How does patronage-driven allocation of public resources affect public trust in democratic institutions in Anambra State?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses will be tested in the study:

- i. H_0 : Patronage-based political appointments have no significant effect on political accountability in Anambra State.
- ii. H_0 : The distribution of government contracts to political allies has no significant effect on citizens' political participation in Anambra State.
- iii. H_0 : Patronage-driven allocation of public resources has no significant effect on public trust in democratic institutions in Anambra State.

2. Review of Related Literature

Political Patronage

Political patronage has been widely conceptualized by scholars as a central feature of political system, particularly in the context of its democratic processes. In general terms, political patronage refers to the practice through which political leaders allocate public resources, positions, and favours to loyal supporters in exchange for their allegiance and political backing rather than on the basis of merit and competence. According to Mari and Tanimu

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(2026), political patronage involves political elites rewarding their loyal followers with government appointments, contracts, and other benefits, a practice that often subordinates meritocratic principles to partisan loyalty and personal allegiance within governance structures. This conceptualization underscores the reciprocal nature of patronage as a mechanism used to secure political loyalty and sustain power within patron-client networks that are prevalent in Nigerian politics. Similarly, Rasak, Oye, Ake, and Raji (2017) describe political patronage in as a clientelistic arrangement where elites, by virtue of their control over state offices, act as patrons who distribute privileges to clients who, in turn, provide political support. Their theoretical overview suggests that such patronage networks create unequal social relations, positioning political elites as gatekeepers of state resources while clients depend on them for access to valued benefits. In an analogous vein, studies examining political godfatherism have framed this phenomenon as a distinct but related expression of political patronage, wherein influential individuals, known as godfathers, exert substantial control over political actors through sponsorship and financial support, thereby shaping political outcomes (Ojo et al., 2023; Lawal, 2025). This view highlights how political patronage is institutionalized in the

Nigerian political landscape through informal yet powerful networks that influence candidate selection, policy decisions, and governance outcomes. From these perspectives, political patronage in the context of this study can be understood as the systematic allocation of public offices, resources, and opportunities by political elites to loyal supporters and networks to secure political allegiance and maintain control over political processes, often at the expense of democratic accountability and meritocratic governance.

Development of Democracy

The development of democracy is a multifaceted concept that has attracted diverse scholarly interpretations, particularly in the context of Nigeria's political evolution. At its core, democratic development refers to the growth, consolidation, deepening, and qualitative improvement of democratic institutions, practices, and values within a polity. In the Nigerian context, scholars have emphasized that democracy goes beyond the mere conduct of periodic elections to include the substantive strengthening of political participation, accountability, rule of law, and social inclusion (Ebegbulem, 2017). Development of democracy, as articulated by this perspective, involves the progressive internalization of democratic norms that enable citizens to meaningfully influence political decision-making and hold leaders

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accountable. This aligns with broader academic definitions that see democratic development as the ongoing process of institutionalising democratic principles such as transparency, inclusiveness, and responsiveness in governance institutions, ensuring that the ideals of democracy are not merely pro forma but substantively realised in practice (Shafiu, Abdullahi, Shafiu & Maulud, 2023; Duhu, Onwo & Onuoha, 2022). Viewed from these perspectives, the development of democracy in the context of this study can be defined as the progressive strengthening and deepening of democratic institutions, norms, and practices that expand meaningful citizen participation, entrench accountability, uphold the rule of law, and enhance the responsiveness of the political system to the needs of the populace.

Patronage-based Political Appointments and Political Accountability in Anambra State.

Patronage-based political appointments have become a significant feature of Nigeria's political system and are widely debated in relation to their implications for political accountability. Political patronage refers to the distribution of public offices and benefits to loyal supporters as a reward for political allegiance rather than on the basis of merit or competence. In many Nigerian states, including Anambra State, political appointments are often influenced by patron-

client relationships were political elites reward loyal party members, financiers, or political associates with strategic government positions. This practice has raised concerns among scholars regarding its potential to weaken political accountability and undermine democratic governance. According to Mari and Tanimu (2025), patronage-driven appointments in the Nigerian public service are frequently determined by political loyalty and personal relationships rather than professional competence, a development that tends to compromise transparency and accountability in governance structures. Such appointments often prioritize political interests over public interest, thereby limiting the ability of government institutions to effectively respond to citizens' needs.

Scholars further argue that when political appointments are based on patronage networks, appointed officials often feel more accountable to the political patrons who facilitated their appointments than to the electorate or democratic institutions. This situation tends to weaken institutional checks and balances, as political appointees may be reluctant to challenge or question the decisions of their benefactors. Emegha, Ofobuiké, Bosah, and Ngwube (2024) observe that the dominance of political appointees over career civil servants in Nigeria has intensified conflicts of interest within

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government institutions, thereby weakening administrative accountability and reducing public confidence in governance processes. In such circumstances, the emphasis on loyalty rather than merit often leads to poor policy implementation, reduced administrative efficiency, and weakened mechanisms of public oversight.

Distribution of Government Contracts to Political Allies and Citizens' Political Participation in Anambra State.

The distribution of government contracts to political allies has become a pervasive practice in Nigerian politics, often linked to patronage networks that influence democratic engagement and citizens' political participation. In the context of Anambra State, the allocation of public contracts to individuals or groups with political connections rather than on the basis of merit can significantly affect the manner and extent to which citizens engage in political processes. According to Okeke and Nwosu (2022), when government contracts are distributed to political loyalists, it creates an environment of exclusivity and favoritism, signaling to ordinary citizens that political participation may not guarantee access to state resources or benefits. This perception can discourage active involvement in elections, public consultations, and other forms of civic engagement, thereby weakening the

participatory dimension of democracy. The authors further noted that such practices often reinforce the dominance of elite networks in the political arena, marginalizing ordinary citizens and reducing their incentive to participate meaningfully in democratic processes.

Scholars have argued that the politicization of contract allocation undermines the principle of equal opportunity in governance, as citizens perceive the political system as serving the interests of a select few rather than the broader public (Chukwuemeka & Eze, 2021). This scenario can foster political apathy, disillusionment, and cynicism among the electorate, as the linkage between participation and tangible benefits appears mediated by political loyalty rather than merit or civic responsibility.

Patronage-driven Allocation of Public Resources and Public Trust in Democratic Institutions in Anambra State.

Patronage-driven allocation of public resources has been identified as a critical factor influencing citizens' trust in democratic institutions, particularly in Nigeria. In the context of Anambra State, the distribution of state resources based on political loyalty rather than merit or equity often undermines perceptions of fairness, transparency, and accountability in governance. Scholars argue that when public resources such as financial allocations,

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development projects, or social services are directed primarily to political supporters, ordinary citizens perceive government institutions as instruments of partisan advantage rather than impartial public service providers (Okeke & Nwosu, 2022). This perception can erode citizens' confidence in the integrity of democratic processes and institutions, as the link between government performance and public welfare becomes mediated by patronage networks rather than institutional efficiency. Similarly, Chukwuemeka and Eze (2021) observe that patronage-driven resource distribution fosters cynicism among citizens, reduces political legitimacy, and diminishes the willingness of the public to engage constructively with democratic processes.

Theoretical Framework

The study is hinged on the Elite Theory. The Elite Theory was first systematically articulated by Gaetano Mosca (1939) and later developed by Vilfredo Pareto (1968) and C. Wright Mills (1956). Mosca posited that in every society, a minority of elites (individuals possessing superior organizational skills, wealth, or political influence) invariably rule and dominate decision-making, while the majority remain passive followers. Pareto emphasized that elites are perpetually in circulation, with some losing power while others rise to maintain societal stability. The central idea of the theory is that

political power is concentrated in the hands of a few, and social and political inequalities are inherent features of governance structures. This perspective underscores that democratic ideals may be undermined by elite manipulation, particularly in contexts where political patronage is prevalent.

Tenets of the Theory

The key tenets of Elite Theory assert that a small fraction of society holds the actual power, controlling policy decisions, resource allocation, and political processes, while the majority exerts little influence. The theory assumes that elites act primarily in their own interests, and that their decisions are often insulated from popular demands or democratic accountability. It also emphasizes the circulation of elites, whereby social mobility allows some non-elites to rise, but the overall concentration of power remains stable. Furthermore, it suggests that political institutions often serve to legitimize elite dominance rather than distribute power equitably, highlighting a structural bias inherent in political systems.

Relevance and Application of the Theory to the Study

The relevance of Elite Theory to this present study lies in its ability to explain how political patronage in Anambra State is used by elites to consolidate power, distribute resources selectively, and influence democratic

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development. Despite criticisms that the theory overemphasizes elite dominance and underestimates citizen agency, it remains applicable by providing a framework to analyze the structural mechanisms through which elites manipulate political processes. By linking the concentration of power to public trust in democratic institutions, the theory enables the study to assess the systemic impact of patronage politics, while acknowledging that citizen frustration or resistance may modify elite strategies over time.

3. Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design in examining the relationship between political patronage and the development of democracy in Anambra State. The choice of the descriptive survey design was considered appropriate because it enabled the researcher to obtain relevant information directly from respondents concerning their perceptions and experiences regarding political patronage and its implications for democratic development without manipulating any of the variables under investigation. The questionnaire served as the

primary instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was structured to obtain relevant responses from the selected respondents in line with the objectives of the study. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to respondents to elicit information on issues relating to political patronage and democratic development in the state. The population of the study consisted of three hundred and twenty-eight (328) selected residents of Anambra State who were considered knowledgeable about political activities and governance in the state. These respondents constituted the accessible population from whom data were collected for the study. The data generated from the questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, and mean scores to summarize and present the responses of the respondents. In addition, inferential statistics, particularly the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC), was employed to test the hypotheses formulated for the study and to determine the nature and strength of the relationship between political patronage and democratic development in Anambra State.

4. Data Presentation and Analysis

4.1 Descriptive Statistics Result

Table 4.1.1: Mean Rating of the Effect of Patronage-based Political Appointments on Political Accountability in Anambra State.

Nri Promise Onyinyechukwu, Nebo Chidiebere .S and Emma E.O. Chukwuemeka

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S/N	Item Description	SA	A	U	D	SD	T	\bar{x}	Decision
1	Patronage-based political appointments often reduce the level of accountability of public office holders in Anambra State.	138	101	39	31	19	328	3.3	Agree
2	Political leaders who are appointed based on personal loyalty tend to prioritize the interests of their political patrons over public interests.	142	115	17	26	28	328	3.3	Agree
3	Patronage-based appointments make it difficult to hold government officials accountable for their actions.	92	104	32	64	36	328	2.9	Disagree
4	When political appointments are based on patronage rather than merit, transparency in governance tends to decline.	136	128	21	18	25	328	3.4	Agree
5	Public officials appointed through political patronage are less likely to be answerable to the general public.	141	88	14	51	34	328	3.2	Agree
Cluster Mean								3.2	

Source: Field Survey, (2026).

Table 4.1.1 shows the mean ratings of respondents on the effect of patronage-based political appointments on political accountability in Anambra State. The result of the analysis reveals that all the questionnaire items used to examine this objective recorded mean scores equal to or above the minimum acceptance threshold of 3.0. This indicates that the respondents generally agreed that

patronage-based political appointments significantly affect political accountability in Anambra State. The implication of this finding is that when political appointments are influenced by patronage rather than merit, public office holders may feel more accountable to their political sponsors than to the general public. This situation can weaken transparency, reduce responsible governance, and undermine effective

Nri Promise Onyinyechukwu, Nebo Chidiebere .S and Emma E.O. Chukwemeka

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oversight in the political system. Consequently, the prevalence of patronage-based appointments may negatively affect the level of accountability

expected in a democratic governance structure in Anambra State

Table 4.1.2: Mean Rating of the Distribution of Government Contracts to Political Allies on Citizens’ Political Participation in Anambra State.

S/N	Item Description	SA	A	U	D	SD	T	\bar{x}	Decision
6	The distribution of government contracts to political allies discourages citizens from actively participating in politics.	101	89	30	81	27	328	3.0	Agree
7	When government contracts are awarded mainly to political loyalists, ordinary citizens feel excluded from the political process.	115	94	22	64	33	328	3.0	Agree
8	Patronage in the awarding of government contracts reduces public interest in political activities.	108	126	18	47	29	328	3.1	Agree
9	Citizens are less motivated to participate in politics when government benefits are limited to political supporters.	131	107	23	53	14	328	3.3	Agree
10	The distribution of government contracts based on political loyalty undermines citizens’ willingness to engage in political processes.	158	113	9	22	26	328	3.4	Agree
Cluster Mean								3.2	

Source: Field Survey, (2026).

Table 4.1.2 shows the mean ratings of respondents on the effect of the distribution of government contracts to political allies on citizens’ political participation in Anambra State. The result of the analysis indicates that all the questionnaire items used to assess this

objective recorded mean scores equal to or above the minimum acceptance threshold of 3.0. This shows that respondents agreed that the distribution of government contracts to political allies significantly affects citizens’ political participation in Anambra State. The implication

Nri Promise Onyinyechukwu, Nebo Chidiebere .S and Emma E.O. Chukwuemeka

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of this finding is that when government contracts are predominantly awarded to political allies, many citizens may feel marginalized and excluded from the benefits of governance. Such perceptions of favoritism can reduce public interest in political processes, weaken citizens' engagement in political activities, and discourage active participation in

democratic practices such as voting, political discussions, and civic involvement. Consequently, the practice of distributing government contracts based on political loyalty may undermine inclusive political participation and weaken the democratic process in Anambra State.

Table 4.1.3: Mean Rating of the Effect Patronage-driven Allocation of Public Resources on Public Trust in Democratic Institutions in Anambra State.

S/N	Item Description	SA	A	U	D	SD	T	\bar{x}	Decision
11	The allocation of public resources based on political patronage reduces public trust in democratic institutions.	116	132	13	41	26	328	3.2	Agree
12	Citizens lose confidence in government institutions when public resources are distributed based on political loyalty.	108	127	16	35	42	328	3.1	Agree
13	When government resources are allocated to political supporters, the credibility of democratic institutions is weakened.	134	92	21	44	37	328	3.2	Agree
14	Unequal distribution of public resources based on political affiliation reduces citizens' trust in government.	81	93	37	69	48	328	2.8	Agree
15	The practice of allocating public resources based on political patronage undermines public confidence in democracy in Anambra State.	123	91	14	61	39	328	3.0	Agree
Cluster Mean								3.1	

Source: Field Survey, (2026).

Table 4.1.3 presents the mean ratings of respondents on the effect of patronage-driven

allocation of public resources on public trust in democratic institutions in Anambra State. The

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result of the analysis reveals that all the questionnaire items used to examine this objective recorded mean scores equal to or above the minimum acceptance threshold of 3.0. This indicates that respondents agreed that patronage-driven allocation of public resources significantly affects public trust in democratic institutions in Anambra State. The implication of this finding is that when public resources are distributed based on political loyalty rather than fairness and merit, citizens may begin to perceive democratic institutions as biased and unjust. Such perceptions can weaken confidence in government agencies, reduce the credibility of democratic processes, and create a sense of

exclusion among members of the public. Consequently, the practice of allocating public resources through political patronage may undermine citizens' trust in democratic institutions and weaken the overall development of democracy in Anambra State.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H₀: Patronage-based political appointments have no significant effect on political accountability in Anambra State.

H₁: Patronage-based political appointments have significant effect on political accountability in Anambra State.

Table 4.2.1: Pearson Correlation of Patronage-Based Political Appointments on Political Accountability in Anambra State

		Patronage-Based Political Appointments	Political Accountability
Patronage-Based Pol. Appoint	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.74*
	Sig(2-tailed)		0.000
	N	328	328
Political Accountability	Pearson Correlation	-0.74*	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	328	328

Table 4.2.1 shows the correlation between patronage-based political appointments and

political accountability in Anambra State. The correlation coefficient ($r = -0.74$, $p = 0.000$)

Nri Promise Onyinyechukwu, Nebo Chidiebere .S and Emma E.O. Chukwuemeka

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indicates a strong negative and statistically significant relationship between patronage-based political appointments and political accountability in Anambra State. Since the correlation value is negative and statistically significant, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that patronage-based political appointments have a significant effect on political accountability in Anambra State. The implication of this finding is that the prevalence of patronage-based political appointments tends to undermine political accountability within the governance system. When political positions are filled based on loyalty and political connections rather than competence and merit, public officials may prioritize the interests of their

political sponsors over the interests of the public. This situation weakens transparency, reduces responsible leadership, and limits the ability of citizens and institutions to effectively hold public office holders accountable. Consequently, patronage-based political appointments negatively affect the level of political accountability necessary for the effective functioning of democracy in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two

H₀: The distribution of government contracts to political allies has no significant effect on citizens' political participation in Anambra State.

H₁: The distribution of government contracts to political allies has significant effect on citizens' political participation in Anambra State.

Table 4.2.2: Pearson Correlation of Distribution of Government Contracts to Political Allies on citizens' political participation in Anambra State.

		Distribution of Government Contracts to Political Allies	citizens' political participation
Dist. of Govt. Contracts to allies	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.81*
	Sig(2-tailed)		0.000
	N	328	328
Citizens Political Participation	Pearson Correlation	-0.81*	1
	Sig(2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	328	328

Nri Promise Onyinyechukwu, Nebo Chidiebere .S and Emma E.O. Chukwuemeka

Table 4.2.2 shows the correlation between the distribution of government contracts to political allies and citizens’ political participation in Anambra State. The correlation coefficient ($r = -0.81$, $p = 0.000$) indicates a very strong negative and statistically significant relationship between the distribution of government contracts to political allies and citizens’ political participation in Anambra State. Since the p-value is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that the distribution of government contracts to political allies has a significant effect on citizens’ political participation in Anambra State. The implication of this finding is that when government contracts are predominantly awarded to political allies rather than through transparent and merit-

based processes, many citizens may feel excluded from the benefits of governance. This perception of favoritism and inequality can discourage citizens from actively engaging in political activities such as voting, political discussions, and civic participation. Consequently, the practice of distributing government contracts based on political patronage may reduce citizens’ motivation to participate in the democratic process in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Three

H₀: Patronage-driven allocation of public resources has no significant effect on public trust in democratic institutions in Anambra State.

H₁: Patronage-driven allocation of public resources has significant effect on public trust in democratic institutions in Anambra State.

Table 4.2.3: Pearson Correlation of Patronage-Driven Allocation of Public Resources on Public Trust in Democratic Institutions in Anambra State.

		Patronage-Driven Allocation of Public Resources	Public Trust in Democratic Institutions
Allocation of resources	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.77*
	Sig(2-tailed)		0.000
	N	328	328
Pub. Trust in Institutions	Pearson Correlation	-0.77*	1
	Sig(2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	328	328

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Table 4.2.3 shows the correlation between patronage-driven allocation of public resources and public trust in democratic institutions in Anambra State. The correlation coefficient ($r = -0.77$, $p = 0.000$) indicates a strong negative and statistically significant relationship between patronage-driven allocation of public resources and public trust in democratic institutions. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that patronage-driven allocation of public resources negatively affects public trust in democratic institutions in Anambra State. The implication of this finding is that when public resources are allocated based on patronage rather than fairness and transparency, citizens perceive the government as biased and unaccountable. This erodes trust in democratic institutions, reduces confidence in governance processes, and may lead to apathy or disengagement from civic and political activities. Therefore, fair and transparent distribution of public resources is critical for strengthening public trust and promoting a healthy democratic environment.

5. Summary of Findings, Conclusions and Recommends

5.1 Findings,

The analysis of the three hypotheses tested revealed the following key findings:

1. Patronage-based political appointments have significant negative effect on political accountability in Anambra State.
2. The distribution of government contracts to political allies has significant negative effect on citizens' political participation in Anambra State.
3. Patronage-driven allocation of public resources has significant negative effect on public trust in democratic institutions in Anambra State.

5.2 Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that political patronage negatively impacts the development of democracy in Anambra State. Patronage-based appointments, biased allocation of government contracts, and patronage-driven distribution of public resources collectively undermine political accountability, discourage citizen participation, and erode public trust in democratic institutions. These practices compromise the principles of transparency, fairness, and inclusivity, which are essential for a healthy democratic system. Therefore, political patronage remains a major obstacle to the consolidation of democratic governance in Anambra State.

5.3 Recommendations

In line with the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

Nri Promise Onyinyechukwu, Nebo Chidiebere .S and Emma E.O. Chukwuemeka

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1. Government and political stakeholders should adopt transparent and merit-based appointment processes for public offices to strengthen political accountability. Ensuring that qualified individuals occupy key positions will enhance oversight, reduce corruption, and promote good governance.

2. Contracts and public projects should be awarded through open, competitive, and transparent processes, minimizing favoritism

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toward political allies. This will encourage citizen confidence in governance and foster active political participation.

3. Public resources should be allocated fairly and based on objective criteria to prevent perceptions of bias and favoritism. Equitable distribution will help restore public trust in democratic institutions and reinforce citizens' confidence in the government's commitment to fairness and inclusivity.

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Nri Promise Onyinyechukwu, Nebo Chidiebere .S and Emma E.O. Chukwuemeka

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Nri Promise Onyinyechukwu, Nebo Chidiebere .S and Emma E.O. Chukwuemeka

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